

REACTIVE ORGANIC NANO-PARTICLES FOR ADVANCED NANOCOMPOSITES

M. Ioelovich and O. Figovsky

Polymate Ltd

E-mail: bd895992@zahav.net.il; P.O.Box 73, Migdal HaEmek 23100, Israel

SUMMARY

Preparation process of reactive organic nano-particles based on renewable and cheap natural celluloses is proposed. The method permits isolation free nano-particles having various reactive functional groups. Application of the reactive nano-fillers for production novel high-quality nanocomposites is discussed. Main features of the reactive nano-particles and nanocomposites are described.

Keywords: Nano-technology, Reactive nano-cellulose, Nano-composites, Structure, Features.

INTRODUCTION

Nano-technology is advanced and quickly developed field of Hi-Tech [1]. The widespread field of nano-technology is development composites contained nano-particles. However, simple mixtures of nano-fillers with polymer binders have limited physical-mechanical properties, because between the components only weak physical bonding is present. To produce high-quality technical nanocomposites, the strong chemical bonds between nano-fillers and binders should be formed. To realize potential of the nano-filler, it should be modified to obtain reactive nano-particles [2]. The modern biomedicine also requires reactive nano-particles to immobilize various types of drugs and biologically active substances (BAS).

The promising raw material for producing reactive organic nano-particles is natural cellulose, because it is widespread, renewable, cheap and biocompatible organic polymer. Moreover, methods chemical modification of cellulose is good developed.

Main purpose of this paper is to describe a process for preparation reactive nano-cellulose particles and to discuss some their application areas

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The process for obtaining organic reactive nano-particles consists of the following basic steps:

Step 1. Intermediate nano-splitting

Cellulose raw material undergoes controlled thermo-chemical-mechanical treatments to prepare wet cake contained agglomerates of nano-particles

Step 2. Chemical modification of surface

Controlled chemical treatment of the wet cake with reagents (R) to introduce on surface of the particles the specific functional groups (FG): aldehyde, carbonyl, carboxyl, epoxy, isocyanate, amine, etc.

Step 3. Size reducing

Controlled atomization of the modified stock to isolate free reactive nano-particles.

As a result, a water dispersion of reactive nano-cellulose particles is obtained. The rod-like particles have size 100 x 30 nm and contain various reactive groups that capable form the strong chemical bonds with polymer binders and various biologically active substances (BAS).

Applications

The reactive nano-particles of modified cellulose can be used to produce high-quality polymer nano-composites, biodegradable nano-materials, nano-glues, as well as biocompatible nano-carriers containing attached drugs and BAS for cosmetics and biomedicine applications.

References

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